

Optimal Hybrid Solar Photovoltaic and Concentrated Solar Power Design for Zimbabwe Baseload Generation

Allen G Njovana^{1*}, Professor Yongsheng Liu¹,

¹ College of Mathematics and Physics, Shanghai University of Electric Power, Shanghai, 200090, P. R. China

Accepted October 15,2021
Published October 22,2021

*Corresponding Author:
Allen G Njovana,
agnallen@hotmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5593093>

Pages: 85-97

Funding: None

Distributed under
Creative Commons CC BY 4.0

Copyright: © The Author(s)

How to cite this article (APA):
A. G. Njovana & Professor Y. S. Liu, (2021). Optimal Hybrid Solar Photovoltaic and Concentrated Solar Power Design for Zimbabwe Baseload Generation. *North American Academic Research*, 4(10), 85-97. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5593093>

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

For the past years until now, Zimbabwe is experiencing power outages that have a drastic impact on the nation's economy, education and health system. The objective of this paper is to propose a scalable optimal solar photovoltaic and concentrated solar power (PV-CSP) hybrid system that can generate electricity to minimize load-shedding and improve electricity access to the nation's population. Considering the geographical location and the availability of the renewable resources, Southern Africa experiences more sun hours in a day compared to wind and rainfall. The installed, hydropower and coal-fired power plants were able to sufficiently meet the energy demands in Zimbabwe, however urbanisation and the growth of the nation's population as well as the increasing number of new energy consuming equipment in the recent years have promoted load-shedding within the country. Fossil fuels are continuously depleting, and climate change has a huge impact on the amount of rainfall which is affecting the hydro-power plants. Considering the decent number of unhindered sun-hours in Zimbabwe, the hybridization of CSP and PV technologies is a promising collaboration. The low cost of PV power production and the dispatchability of CSP, coupled with thermal energy storage (TES), can deliver electricity, stabilize the grid and meet the energy demands at a lower cost than what could be achieved with CSP alone or with PV alone. The integration of CSP and PV has a high possibility of reducing the levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) with the least greenhouse gas emission compared to other hybrids integrated with fossil-fuel. PV-CSP hybrid may have an increase in capital costs and sometimes the cost of electricity however, large scale integration of PV and CSP can have a slight increase in the cost of electricity at night as both the systems will be using their stored energy, but a guaranteed stable grid will be provided.

Keywords: RENEWABLE ENERGY; PHOTOVOLTAIC; CONCENTRATED SOLAR; HYBRID; THERMAL ENERGY STORAGE; BATTERY ENERGY STORAGE.

Introduction

Zimbabwe continues to struggle with load shedding due to the continuous growth of the country's

population and the migration to urban centres that have resulted in increased power demands. Due to these factors, the grid failed to generate enough energy to meet national demand or pay for adequate power imports. Zimbabwe's electricity demand is estimated between 1500 MW and 2000 MW depending on season while the current total generation capacity is a mere 1300MW leaving the country with a huge power deficit that can only be mitigated by expensive imports from Mozambique and South Africa ^[1]. Initially, the country had an installed generation capacity of just over 2,000 MW hydropower, and 920MW from the Coal Thermal Power Plants but currently the generation capacity is only 45% ^[2].

Currently, Zimbabwe relies more on coal for energy generation even though the country is endowed with abundant renewable energy resources such as solar and hydropower near natural landmarks such as Victoria Falls, not to mention biomass, geothermal, and to a lesser extent wind power all these present a great opportunity for investment. According to [Wagner 2021 geology of coal](#), the rate at which coal is being currently produced has estimated that the coal is expected to last for the next 110 years, as compared to reserves of oil and gas which are expected to last from 52 and 54 years respectively. Although hydropower is considered a stable form of renewable energy source, in recent years Kariba South was expanded to generate an additional 300MW, but the station has become vulnerable to climate variability and is not capable of generating enough power due to lower water levels in the lake next to it due to climate change ^[3]. Droughts became a major threat making it difficult to plan and provide a stable and reliable grid.

As the power shortages persist with no coherent government/power provider strategy to tackle the challenge, it has become comprehensible that this is from many years of poor planning and lack of strategic thinking. Zimbabwe's population has doubled from 7.4 million in 1980 to about 14.6 million in 2019 and with it the demand for energy increased, but there has been no corresponding growth in energy generation.

This study will assist in:

- designing an optimal hybrid of solar PV and CSP technologies with the aim of curtailing the power outages and meet the country's energy demands,
- selecting the suitable hybrid for Zimbabwe that has high energy yield and low limitations,
- selecting the ideal energy storage systems (ESS) that can be coupled with the hybrid system,
- analyzing technological and economical barriers for the implementation of the hybrid, and
- proving that the combination of the two technologies will not only save the country's problems but will also have an impact based on producing clean and affordable power to the country's population.

Materials and methods

I. Solar PV and CSP technology

Zimbabwe receives a decent amount of solar that is capable of both PV and CSP plants according to various sources. For a PV-CSP plant to be economically viable, the most important factor is that the location must have good Direct Normal Irradiance (DNI) which is a quantity of great interest to CSP installations, and Diffuse Horizontal Irradiance (DHI) which is ideal for bi-facial PV modules, and Global Horizontal Irradiance

(GHI) which is of great interest to PV installations as it includes both DNI and DHI which is necessary when analyzing the incoming solar radiation on solar PV modules [4]. The best solar irradiated place in Zimbabwe has an accumulated annual DNI and GHI of approximately 2400 kWh/m² and 2200 kWh/m² respectively and it receives a reasonable number of sun-hours per day [5].

Figure 1: Zimbabwe’s western province DNI and GHI [5].

The specific location chosen is in the western part of Zimbabwe and it receives approximately an average of 6.5 kWh/m² of DNI daily which increases significantly to 8.15 kWh/m² in October (summer). According to the same source there is very little hindrance in the region, which makes it an ideal location to employ the use of solar technologies. The nation’s biggest hydro-power plant is also located in the same province which will also make it much easier to connect to the grid.

Solar Harnessing Technologies

The technologies for harnessing solar energy come in many different forms to suit different circumstances. There are two principal and currently available solar harnessing technologies for large scale power generation that use completely different systems of harvesting solar energy: *solar photovoltaic* and *solar thermal* [6]. One, directly converts solar radiation into electricity while the other, concentrates the same solar radiation onto one focal point with the objective of raising the temperature of the heat transfer fluid (HTF) up to a desired level. Although the two technologies have unlike methods of harvesting solar energy, they both cover a wide range of applications, from simple domestic water heating systems to utility-scale electricity production.

Figure 2: Solar PV and CSP technologies.

Currently on the renewable energy market, solar PV is the most cost-effective with prices continuously decreasing while the technology and output capacity per module keep increasing every year. According to the [International Energy Agency \(IEA\)](#) reports, the LCOE of PV systems are below retail electricity prices in several countries and are getting lower approaching the level of generation costs of other conventional sources. To an added advantage, the technology is highly scalable and modular, and so can be applied practically anywhere ^[7].

Unlike solar PV, CSP technologies mainly utilize optical/reflective devices such as mirrors and lenses to concentrate the sunlight mainly DNI onto a desired focal point where a secondary energy carrier usually a heat transfer fluid (HTF), like molten salts or synthetic oil is located which is later used in a heat exchanger to generate steam and later electricity ^[8]. CSP systems offer a favorable advantage that is, they can store solar energy in the form of heat to be used later in the evenings and night when the sun is not shining. This can help reach the goal of making solar energy fully cost-competitive.

II. Ideal Hybrid for Zimbabwe

Solar energy offers the most and significant advantages, and it gives the chance to provide a stable and yet predictable electricity costs for a very long time. Once after capital expenditure (CAPEX), the costs of keeping a solar power plant running are much lower and will eventually decrease with time compared to fossil fuel power plants. Solar energy is different from other sources like wind and hydro because they can be interfered with the environment and climate change. In other words, solar will always be available every day for a certain number of hours but wind speed or rainfall changes due to different weather and seasons which makes it difficult for providers to plan a grid or determine the national energy supply.

Even though a megawatt of CSP requires more land than a megawatt of PV, one thing to remember is that both technologies rely on the sun, but they harness solar radiation differently. Therefore, to have a reliable, affordable, dispatchable clean power, the two technologies can be combined considering the advantages of each. With the aim of achieving a much higher energy yield with less technological or environmental

limitations, the desired PV-CSP power plant will employ the use of bifacial PV modules and will use the parabolic trough collector technology on the CSP side.

Bifacial modules can generate electricity from the sun shining directly on them and from the sunlight reflected on the opposite side/underneath the module. Diffused light from clouds, buildings, or other objects can also be reflected on the back of the module and generate electricity providing an increased total energy generation [9]. Thus, they offer many advantages compared to traditional modules that generate electricity from only one side of the module. The top solar cells function like those of a conventional solar panel array. The bottom solar cells absorb light that is reflected off the ground or from other surfaces without being absorbed. This light is called *albedo* light. White or light color surface reflect better than dark colors. Demonstration of a bifacial module operation based on direct, diffuse, and reflected irradiance and its estimated output gain (G) capacity referred to as: $G_{\text{rear}} = G_{\text{diffuse}} + G_{\text{reflected}}^{(\text{albedo})}$ can be seen below.

Figure 3: Bifacial modules and their operation.

Studies have proven that bifacial solar modules can generate additional energy yield depending on the reflectiveness of the surface. A generation of up to 30% more energy from the rear side can be realized depending on installation conditions, environment and geographic locations [10]. To generate more power from fixed bifacial properties or ones with tracking system, bifacial modules require a higher tilted mounting that allows and gives room for the reflected light to bounce back at the rear of the modules as this will lower shadowing from the rear leading to higher bifacial gain.

Installation Area	Albedo	Generation Gain
Grass	15%	12%
Sand	25%	14.5%
Gravel	33%	21%
White painted concrete	90%	28%

Table 1: Bifacial gain based on area of installation.

Parabolic trough collector (PTC) power plants use parabolic collectors to reflect sunlight onto a tubular receiver also known as a “Dewar tube” positioned in the line of the parabola. The Dewar tube contains the HTF travelling from the cold tank that then absorbs and transfers the heat via a circulation to the heat exchanger to produce steam. The produced steam is used to drive a steam turbine, which on its part drives the electric generator. This type of solar concentration can provide an output fluid temperature ranging over 400°C. Once the HTF is heated, it is stored in the hot tank that can prevent heat loss and the stored heat energy can be used later or directly discharged at a specified flow rate to heat water and generate steam for the steam cycle [11]. The configurations of PTC vary with HTFs and the inclusion of thermal energy storage system (TES). For the HTF medium, molten salts, synthetic oil or water are the main common fluids however, some HTF are cheaper but are difficult to implement in a TES system due to the rate at which they lose heat [12]. In figure 4 below, orange color represents the HTF which is thermal oil, and the storage medium is shown in grey which is molten salt (it is also possible to use molten salts as both the HTF and storage medium). The water and steam circuit are shown in blue, and **G** represents the generator. Due to the listed advantages, the favored type of PTC configuration for the proposal is a trough system with a two-tank direct molten salts TES, as shown in the figure below.

Figure 4: Parabolic Trough Collector plant configuration.

To summarize, the hybridization of solar PV and CSP has a large impact in reduction of CO₂ emissions. The hybrid can also significantly lower the LCOE and provide a much stable grid that is able to meet the nation’s energy demands.

III. Energy Storage Systems

Storage is needed in PV systems to overcome the intermittency of the energy generated. These variations could be caused due to daily or monthly solar irradiance fluctuations. Daily fluctuation occurs as a result of the

change of solar irradiance within the 24-hour period, while the seasonal (or monthly) fluctuations occur due to the change of solar irradiance across the summer and winter [14]. PV system will not generate the same amount of energy each month. Thus, another complementary system to help even out the energy difference throughout the year is needed. This system allows us to collect and store the energy generated by the sun during daytime in order to release it later on demand. This can be a situation when sufficient power is produced during the day while excess is being stored, and later the stored energy is used during the night. Also, when insolation conditions are ideal, the solar system may produce enough power for the target application, but on dull days, direct energy supply from collectors is diminished, and the energy from the storage is used to compensate the deficit [13]. Energy storage system also help to improve and smooth out differences and minor fluctuations in energy supply caused by shading, passing clouds, weather conditions, etc.

The **PV section** of the hybrid will be coupled with a lithium iron phosphate (LFP) BESS considering the battery technology’s power density and depth of discharge (DOD) that make it more suitable for long term utility scale storage. There are several critical functions that a BESS is expected to perform including peak shaving, load and time shifting, meet peak demand and provide energy autonomy and emergency backup [15]. In general, peak load problems could be reduced, electrical stability could be improved, and power quality disturbances could be eliminated. Battery energy storage offers a flexible and multifunctional role in the grid of electric power supply, by assuring more efficient management of available power for consumers. As supply from PV components varies due to its intermittency, energy must be provided to rapidly restore the frequency to within the desired limits [16]. This application is ideal for high-power batteries because they can respond quickly, and the energy requirement is low. BESS allow to shift energy usage by charging batteries with solar energy and discharging them during peak load when electricity is also more expensive, and the sun is not shining or when there are unexpected power cuts.

Figure 5: BESS charging and discharging for load leveling.

Battery energy storage can be deployed in different locations depending on the size and purpose of the ESS. It can be applied at the power plant where the renewable energy source (RES) is, in support of the

transmission network, at various points in the distribution areas or in residential areas where the electricity demand is high.

Figure 6: BESS deployed in area of distribution near load center.

On the **CSP section**, PTC TES generally consist of two indirect tanks using molten salts as the storage medium. In contrast to the similar direct systems, indirect storage systems are characterized by using different fluids one as the HTF (thermal oil) and one as the storage medium (molten salt). The main reason for the shift from a direct to an indirect system lies in the fact that the two fluids have different properties which makes one suitable for a certain role [17]. With the operating temperature of PTC, the required tank volumes become larger. As the adoption of TES in CSP plants leads to increased capital costs, it might be expected that the LCOE would also increase. However, research state that the LCOE is much higher in systems with no storage, making the implementation of TES convenient from an economic point of view. Molten salts are the ideal storage medium as they lose only about 1 degree of heat a day, which makes it more profitable to use the stored energy daily and get paid for the daily and nightly deliveries of electricity. The storage medium can be heated and cooled daily for at least 30 years until the storage tanks need corrosion repair.

Figure 7: PTC power plant with two tank indirect TES.

IV. Hybrid Expenditures

The LCOE of the proposed hybrid plant is the combination of all the cash inputs divided by the combined electricity production of all the plant components during its lifetime. The LCOE calculations can be represented as: $CAPEX_{CSP}$, $CAPEX_{PV}$ and $CAPEX_{BESS}$ are the investment costs of the CSP plant, PV plant and the BESS respectively. The fixed yearly operational and maintenance costs of the components and equipment are given by $OPEX_{CSP}$, $OPEX_{PV}$ and $OPEX_{BESS}$ respectively. N and n correspond to the total and current year of the project respectively. This grand total is done using a discount rate (DR). FYE_{CSP} , FYE_{PV} and FYE_{BESS} represent the first-year electrical output of each plant component/system. Since PV performance degrades with time, so a degradation factor (SDR) is considered [19]. Also, the battery performance degrades with time, characterized in terms of the number of cycles and has been considered within the FYE_{BESS} prior to the LCOE calculation. The CSP plant also has a degradation factor, but the value is so small that it is considered negligible.

$$LCOE = \frac{CAPEX_{CSP} + \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{OPEX_{CSP}}{(1+DR)^n} + CAPEX_{PV} + \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{OPEX_{PV}}{(1+DR)^n} + CAPEX_{BESS} + \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{OPEX_{BESS}}{(1+DR)^n}}{\sum_{n=1}^N \frac{FYE_{CSP} + FYE_{BESS} + FYE_{PV} \times (1-SDR)^n}{(1+DR)^n}}$$

Figure 8: Total installation costs of a 100MW PTC plant.

The 67% investment cost over the construction of a 100MW PTC power plant constitutes mostly of the solar field, power block and TES though this depends on the local cost of land and labor and the amount of thermal storage as the costs of the power block are similar to those of a fossil-fuel fired power block. Other costs range between 5% - 8% as they mostly operation expenditures that will be incurred on a monthly basis and other contingencies. In general, CSP plants require large amounts of investment compared to PV however, CSP with ESS offers more advantages compared to PV with BESS. This can be proven considering the storage capacity of both plants, TES can operate for up to 30 years while BESS have a lifespan of up to 10 years, yet

the technology is considered expensive.

V. Hybrid Limitations and Feasibility

There are some inherent limitations to combining PV and CSP including turbine start-up/shut-down, turbine ramping limits, part load turbine efficiency, and grid connection. The limitations seem to have more impact on the CSP section of the hybrid; however, some are minor but with regards to turbine start-up and shutdown, there is one hybrid PV-CSP plant operation mode that is practical which is the baseload demand can be covered by the PV system only, with the CSP system shut-down for that period in the day. This daily start-up and shut-down operation routine can lead to increased maintenance costs and overhauls of the turbine [18]. Start-up and shut-down cycling of steam turbines can lead to high thermo mechanical stresses, thermal fatigue, rotor fracture, blade erosion amongst other detrimental consequences that reduce the life of the turbine [18]. However, a PV-CSP plant operation modes can be designed in a way that minimizes turbine shut-down and the plant performance is dependent on the strategy of operation implemented.

For this proposed hybrid plant, the operating strategy consists of different operating modes (OM), two of which are described. The TES is charged by the energy from the solar field and discharges at a flow rate depending on how much power is needed to supplement the PV. The PV power is constrained so that the turbine power never drops under its minimum value, in case of any surplus energy from the PV it is used to charge the BESS but if the BESS is fully charged the surplus energy is curtailed. This is when both the systems are on-line. If the TES has enough energy to supply the demand, no flow enters the TES hot tank, which simply discharges at the nominal flow rate. No power will be coming from the PV and the BESS will be idle.

In a simplified expression, the three main operation modes are as follows:

1. If energy from the PV modules can meet the energy demand therefore, PV system runs alone. Excess energy can be stored in the BESS and the collected energy from the CSP system can all be stored in a TES tank.
2. If the energy from the PV modules cannot meet the energy demand, therefore PV modules and BESS are both used for energy generation. The collected energy from the CSP system can all be stored in a TES tank.
3. If the energy of PV modules and BESS cannot meet the energy demand, PV modules, BESS and CSP system are all used for energy generation.

As of 2021, South Africa has 500MW operational CSP plants with another additional 200MW under construction and it is one of the few African countries to employ the use of PV-CSP hybrid [19]. Since the paper's research is for Zimbabwe a neighboring country of South Africa, the presence of the 271MW South Africa's Redstone PV-CSP hybrid works as a supporting figure to prove the feasibility of such hybrids in Southern Africa region.

Figure 9: South Africa's Redstone PV-CSP hybrid.

Conclusion

PV-CSP hybrids may offer more economical ways of producing high-capacity factor power generation than CSP alone or PV alone. This interest has been driven by solar energy companies such as Solar Paces which is leading with the designing and providing solutions for CSP systems. The concept is that since PV generally has a lower LCOE than CSP but has the most expensive storage system, PV will operate during the day providing baseload electricity as well as charging the BESS. CSP with TES operates only as a supplement to PV during the day in case of any demands. The CSP system will be storing the heat during the day so that it will be connected during peak load and at night as the BESS has a certain DOD which normally lasts for four hours while TES can range between eight to twelve hours. For a PV-CSP plant to be economically viable, the most important factor is that the location must have good solar resources, both DNI and GHI, and must be a location that receives a reasonable number of sun-hours per day.

The concept of PV-CSP hybrid plants is one of great interest, especially in regions such as Southern Africa where the weather and climate conditions are favorable for such projects. This is evident with the development of PV-CSP hybrid plants, such as Redstone in South Africa and six other CSP power plants and Zambia's new Kululushi plant, which is the country's first 200MW CSP power plant. Zimbabwe is attractive of high-capacity solar plants since there is a very good solar resource, land is abundant some of which is barren, and in some areas, there are no opportunities hydro-power due to lack of sufficient water bodies. Solar only hybrid power cannot be the sole source of electricity to provide a stable grid but has the capability of reducing the use of conventional energy sources. The environmental benefits of the hybrid system can be assessed in terms of avoided emissions. Given that a conventional thermal power plant emits a certain amount of pollutant per kWh of generated electricity, the hybrid system can be considered to cause an avoidance of emissions, since it generates the electricity with nearly zero CO₂ emissions.

Specific frameworks and financial incentives are required for such projects to take place. PV-CSP hybrid

system requires large amounts of investments therefore, a high performance and dispatchable grid with a minimum operation expenditure (OPEX) can be viable and offer the chance to plan and predict the grid's consumption rates. The LCOE can be low, but the number of consumers relying on the grid makes it possible for the providers/investors to realize their return on investment after a few years of connecting to the grid. PV-CSP systems require large amounts of investment which somehow restricts private investors however, if government incentives and support could be given to the interested investors, there is a possibility of producing clean and cheaper energy for the country.

References

- [1]. Daniel Jones| “Refurbishment delays hamper Zimbabwe energy prospects,” [Available online]: <http://lowveldpost.co.zw/2021/05/20/refurbishment-delays-hamper-zimbabwe-energy-prospects/> -May 2021.
- [2]. Dubé, K. Vanderwal and Godwell Nhamo. “Vulnerability of nature-based tourism to climate variability and change: Case of Kariba resort town, Zimbabwe.” *Journal of outdoor recreation and tourism* 29 (2020): 100281.
- [3]. Emiliano Bellini, “Zimbabwe set for real solar growth.” [Available Online]: <https://www.pv-magazine.com/2020/01/24/zimbabwe-set-for-real-solar-growth/> | January 2020.
- [4]. Vignola, Frank. GHI Correlations with DHI and DNI and the Effects of Cloudiness on one-minute Data. (2012).
- [5]. Solargis, “The World Bank, Global Solar Atlas 2.0: Solar resource data.” (2020)
- [6]. Rashad, Mohamed. K., Adel A. El-Samahy, Mohamed Daowd and Amr M. A. Amin. “A comparative Study on Photovoltaic and Concentrated Solar Thermal Power Plants.” (2015).
- [7]. IRENA, “Renewable Energy Technologies: Cost Analysis Series; Solar Photovoltaics,” Volume 1: Power Sector Issue 4/5, (2012).
- [8]. IRENA, “Renewable Energy Technologies: Cost Analysis Series; Concentrating Solar Power,” Volume 1: Power Sector Issue 2/5, (2012).
- [9]. Chris Deline, Silvana Ayala Peláez, Bill Marion. Bifacial PV System Performance: Separating Fact from Fiction | PVSC-46, Chicago, IL (2019).
- [10]. Gerritsen, Eric & Janssen, Gaby & Deline, Chris. A "global" view on bifacial gain: dependence on geographic location and environmental conditions. 10.1049/PBPO107E. (2018).
- [11]. H. Zhang, J. Baeyens, J. Degreve and G. Caceres, “Concentrated solar power plants: Review and design methodology,” *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, no. 22, pp. 466-481, (2013).
- [12]. Py, Xavier & Sadiki, Najim & Olives, Régis & Goetz, Vincent & Falcoz, Quentin. (2017). Thermal energy storage for CSP (Concentrating Solar Power). EPJ Web of Conferences. 148. 00014. 10.1051/epjconf/201714800014. EIA: Battery Storage in the United States: An Update on Market Trends | (2020).

- [13]. Electric Energy Storage Technology Options: A White Paper Primer on Applications, Costs, and Benefits. EPRI, Palo Alto, CA, 1020676 (2010).
- [14]. Asian Development Bank (ADB), “Handbook on battery energy storage system”: TCS189791-2 (2018).
- [15]. NERC “Energy Storage Impacts of Electrochemical Utility-Scale Battery Energy Storage Systems on the Bulk Power System” | (IS-2021-123)- (2021).
- [16]. T. Mehr, M. Masoum, Nasim Jabalameli: Grid-connected Lithium-ion battery energy storage system for load leveling and peak shaving| (2013).
- [17]. R. Guedez, J. Spelling and B. Laumert, “Reducing the Number of Turbine Starts in Concentrating Solar Power Plants Through the Integration of Thermal Energy Storage,” *Journal of Solar Engineering*, vol. 137, pp. 1-8, (2014).
- [18]. Larchet, Kevin. “Solar PV-CSP Hybridisation for Baseload Generation: A Techno-economic Analysis for the Chilean Market.” (2015).
- [19]. Nandu Bhula, Christo Spammer, “Dispatchable Solar Energy 24/7, The Case of Bokpoort CSP plant in South Africa.” (2021).

© 2021 by the authors. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

Author(s) have identified their affiliated institutions or organizations, along with the corresponding country or geographic region. NAAR, TWASP remains neutral with regard to any jurisdictional claims.

